

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831926>

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Annotatsiya: *Buxgalteriya balansida korxonaning moliya-xo'jalik faoliyati to'g'risida katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlar: korxonaning mulkiy holati, moliyaviy resurslarning mavjudligi, ularning taqsimlanishi va foydalanilishi, moliyaviy natijalar (foyda)ning kapitalizatsiyasi, o'z va qarz mablag'lari, pul mablag'larining mavjudligi va holati, debitorlik va kreditorlik qarzlarning holati, asosiy vositalar, nomoddiy aktivlarning holati va o'zgarishi va shu kabilar haqida ma'lumotlar taqdim qilinadi. Korxonada va tashkilotlarda xo'jalik faoliyatini boshqarish bevosita mablag'larning holatiga, ulardan foydalanish darajasiga, mablag'larning aylanish tezligiga bog'liq. Balansni iqtisodiy jihatdan olganda xo'jalik mablag'larini joylanishi va tashkil topish manbalari bo'yicha bir-biriga tengligini ta'minlaydi deb aytsak bo'ladi.*

Annotatsiya: *In the accounting balance sheet, large-scale information about the financial and economic activities of the enterprise is presented: the property status of the enterprise, the availability and use of financial resources, the capitalization of financial results (profits), the availability and status of own and borrowed funds, the status of receivables and creditworthiness, the status and change of fixed assets, intangible assets, etc. Management of economic activity in enterprises and organizations directly depends on the state of funds, the level of their use, the speed of circulation of funds. It can be said that when taking the balance sheet economically, it ensures that the economic funds are equal to each other in terms of location and sources of organization.*

Kalit so'zlar: Balans tushunchasi, buxgalteriya balans, aktiv, passiv, hisobot davrlari, kapital, majburiyat.

Key words: *balance sheet concept, balance sheet, asset, passive, reporting periods, capital, commitment.*

The balance sheet is a method of economic grouping and generalization by types of Economic funds, sources of organization, expressed in money for a certain date. Thus, the basis of the structure of the balance sheet is the economic content of Economic funds and sources of their organization. With the help of the balance sheet, it is possible to have clear information about the funds attributed to the enterprise and organizations themselves, borrowed funds, funds received for temporary use, and secondly, if it gives

the opportunity to control the state of funds, then the third is the basis for studying the types of funds. Substances in the asset and passive of the balance sheet are grouped into two sections in accordance with the economic classification of funds by composition, location and sources of organization.

The balance sheet is said to be on two sides, its left side is said to be active and its right side is said to be passive. The structure of the asset of the balance sheet of the Enterprise includes the following sections:

I. Long -term assets; II. Current assets.

Passive, on the other hand, houses the following departments:

I. Sources of Own Funds; II. Liabilities.

Assets cover investments owned by a particular person or business organization, including cash and of a certain value, including real estate in a business, vehicle, furniture and equipment, inventory and the share quality of other organizations. Cash funds that manifest liquidity are cash, money in the bank, fixed deposit receipts (BDT), which are considered current assets. In addition, prepaid expenses are also an outline of the current asset. Liabilities are bonds in a business, existing debts, or claims from outside participants and creditors. Examples of passives are authorized utility costs and tax costs, including creditors (those who receive products on loan from suppliers of goods), bank debts, unpaid business debts. As with current assets, current liabilities are liabilities paid by the firm within one year from the date of the balance sheet. The correlation of the individual sections in the balance sheet asset and passive can be shown as follows.

Types of balance sheet

There are different types of balance sheet, which are characterized by the following signs:

- according to the time of the structure of the moment;
- according to the volume of information in the moment;
- according to the form of ownership;
- according to the object of reflection;
- according to the method of cleaning.

The balance of entry is drawn up during the organization of the enterprise. It sets the sum of the wealth at which the enterprise begins its activities. In the balance of entry, the authorized capital is reflected in the form of monetary funds, other property,

and so on, according to the Constituent documents and contributions to it. Current balances are drawn up in time at the time specified by the legislation of the enterprise. (Monthly, quarterly, semi-annual, annual). Based on the data of foreign literature, the balance sheet of accounting is recorded before the formation of the test balance. The test balance is the result of the debit and credit balance of all calculations. The amount on the debit side in the test balance is according to the date of its conclusion to the amount on the credit side

Figure 2. Principles of forming an accounting balance sheet

The correctness of the balance sheet is ensured by the completeness and quality of the documents on which it is based when drawing up the balance sheet. If during the reporting period all transactions of economic activity were not documented or incorrectly formalized in time, then the balance sheet does not reflect the actual end of the enterprise's work. Each article of the balance sheet must be approved with documents, records in accounting schemes, accounting calculations and inventory.

Let's consider the content of the principles of the formation of the balance sheet:

1. Balance beam. This principle of balance sheet formation ensures the reliability of the account and preliminary documents on the basis of which indicators are formed. If there are cases when some kind of economic facts are not appropriately confirmed or incorrectly formalized, confusing (distorted) information is reflected in the balance sheet of the enterprise.

2. Balance sheet validity. This principle implies compliance with the assessment of the objects of the account with the data reflected in the corresponding lines of the balance sheet.

3. Unit of balance. This principle indicates that the balance sheet is formed on the basis of unified principles of accounting and assessment.

4. The duration of the balance. This principle of balance formation means that each subsequent balance comes from the balance sheet indicators before it. For example, the final balance on the results of the previous year should be the initial balance for the reporting year.

5. Accuracy of balance. This principle is explained by the ease with which all those who have compiled a balance sheet and read and analyze it can understand. In our opinion, compliance with the above principles in the formation of the balance sheet allows us to ensure the correctness, truthfulness and comparability of the information contained in it.

APPENDIX

Balance sheet-a table that expresses economic funds, their composition, location and sources of their occurrence in money for a certain date

Balance-the term "balance" is derived from the Latin words "BIS" - twice, "banx" - scales of boub, literally meaning "two blacks", and is used as the concept of equality, balance

The term active-comes from the Latin term active, to act, to exist.

Passive - (lot. inactive) unbiased posture is derived from the root of words such as explanation. The passive part of the balance sheet reflects obligations and private equity.

The reporting period is the date on which the economic entity is required to draw up an accounting report.

Obligation-obligation, promise, duty, duty, correspondence; civil legal relations formalized by the contract.

Capital (nem. capital-the main property; lot.capitalis - the most important, the main, the head) - there are such types of funds that are intended to be aimed at some goal, such as initial, constant, variable, basic and working capital.

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